

Cortical mapping of mismatch responses to independent acoustic features

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Abstract

Predictive coding is an influential theory of neural processing underlying perceptual inference. However, it is unknown to what extent prediction violations of different sensory features are mediated in different regions in auditory cortex, with different dynamics, and by different mechanisms. This study investigates the neural responses to synthesized acoustic syllables, which could be expected or unexpected, along several features. By using electrocorticography (ECoG) in rat auditory cortex (subjects: adult female Wistar rats with normal hearing), we aimed at mapping regional differences in mismatch responses to different stimulus features.

Continuous streams of morphed syllables formed roving oddball sequences in which each stimulus was repeated several times (thereby forming a standard) and subsequently replaced with a deviant stimulus which differed from the standard along one of several acoustic features: duration, pitch, interaural level differences (ILD), or consonant identity. Each of these features could assume one of several different levels, and the resulting change from standard to deviant could be larger or smaller. The deviant stimuli were then repeated to form new standards. We analyzed responses to the first repetition of a new stimulus (deviant) and its last repetition in a stimulus train (standard). For the ECoG recording, we implanted urethane-anaesthetized rats with 8×8 surface electrode arrays covering a 3×3 mm cortical patch encompassing primary and higher-order auditory cortex.

We identified the response topographies and latencies of population activity evoked by acoustic stimuli in the rat auditory regions, and mapped their sensitivity to expectation violations along different acoustic features. For all features, the responses to deviant stimuli increased in amplitude relative to responses to standard stimuli. Deviance magnitude did not further modulate these mismatch responses. Mismatch responses to different feature violations showed a heterogeneous distribution across cortical areas, with no evidence for systematic topographic gradients for any of the tested features. However, within rats, the spatial distribution of mismatch responses varied more between features than the spatial distribution of tone-evoked responses. This result supports the notion that prediction error signaling along different stimulus features is subserved by different cortical populations, albeit with substantial heterogeneity across individuals.

1. Introduction

Auditory processing allows the brain to transform vibrations of the eardrum into abstracted auditory perceptions. Successful listening requires not only tracking stable auditory objects, but also detecting unexpected changes to the auditory scene. Mismatch negativity (MMN) is one of the most well-studied physiological correlates of deviance detection in the auditory system. When presented with unexpected input, brain activity recorded using electroencephalography in humans exhibits a well-described pattern of neural response waveforms showing an enhanced response to novel stimuli. Conversely, repetitive, and therefore expected, stimulation leads to reduced responses. The difference in response waveforms between responses to unexpected as opposed to expected stimuli is known as the MMN, and it is well defined based on previous studies in humans (Näätänen, 1990).

MMN is a macroscopic signature of deviance detection, derived from bulk measures of neural activity such as electroencephalogram (EEG). Meso- and microscopic correlates of mismatch responses have also been described at the level of small neuronal populations (multi-units) and single neurons along the auditory pathway, showing an increased response amplitude to a novel stimulus (oddball) relative not only to a repeated standard stimulus (Malmierca et al., 2009), but also to a control stimulus that is predictable but not repeated (Nieto-Diego and Malmierca, 2016), suggesting true deviance detection. This particular type of adaptation, known as stimulus-specific adaptation (SSA), quantifies the changing neuronal firing rates to a deviant stimulus compared with a standard. SSA can be observed in both primary and secondary areas of the auditory cortex (Antunes et al., 2010; Duque et al., 2016; Malmierca et al., 2009; Nieto-Diego and Malmierca, 2016; Parras et al., 2017; Richardson et al., 2013; Ulanovsky et al., 2003; Von Der Behrens et al., 2009). SSA responses are thought to reflect deviance detection mechanisms at the microscopic level, and they have been suggested to form a counterpart of the MMN which is a more macroscopic response detectable on the scalp (Escera and Malmierca, 2014; Nieto-Diego and Malmierca, 2016; Ulanovsky et al., 2003).

Traditionally, two main, not necessarily mutually exclusive, hypotheses have been put forward to interpret these physiological observations. According to the “model adjustment hypothesis” (Saarinen et al., 1992), the MMN reflects an online update of the prior perceptual model, previously established due to sensory experience, by comparing it with actual auditory input. Meanwhile, the adaptation hypothesis (May et al., 1999) claims that the attenuation of the response to standard stimuli could be simply due to neural adaptation. More recently, these hypotheses have been united under the predictive coding framework, according to which the brain entails and continuously revises an internal model of the world. In this theory, the model updates are based on prediction error signals, which result from comparing the internal model predictions with the actual sensory inputs (Auksztulewicz and Friston, 2016; Bastos et al., 2012; Friston, 2005). When sensory information reaches a given stage of sensory or cortical processing, it is suppressed by

predictions signalled from higher-order stages in a descending (top-down) manner. If new sensory information cannot be predicted by the brain's internal model, the resulting prediction errors are propagated in a bottom-up (ascending) manner to higher-order regions and update the subsequent predictions. Hence, lower and higher cognitive stages keep communicating through reciprocal pathways, with descending connections mediating prediction signalling, and ascending connections mediating prediction error signalling. This results in a gradual suppression of prediction error signalling (model adjustment) and a rapid decrease of synaptic efficacy (adaptation) when a deviant stimulus is first encountered and then repeated to form a standard. Specifically, according to the model adjustment hypothesis, the MMN is thought to reflect an online update of the prior perceptual model, based on a comparison between previous sensory experience and the actual auditory input (Saarinen et al., 1992). Unlike the model adjustment hypothesis, the adaptation hypothesis claims that the attenuation of the response to standard stimuli could be simply due to neural adaptation (Jääskeläinen et al., 2004; May et al., 1999; May and Tiitinen, 2010).

While prediction error suppression is a widely accepted theory explaining mismatch responses, it has been suggested that predictions and prediction errors corresponding to different stimulus features are mediated by different neural populations, and even different mechanisms (Auksztulewicz et al., 2018; Stefanics et al., 2019). On the other hand, in animal studies, although mismatch responses have been shown to occur following changes in repetitive syllable patterns (Ahmed et al., 2011; Mahmoudzadeh et al., 2017), syllable duration (Lipponen et al., 2019) and acoustic frequency (Eriksson and Villa, 2005), no robust regional differences to various stimulus features have been identified. Directly comparing results of studies in animal models and human volunteers is challenging because of methodological differences: while most animal studies apply a classical MMN design with a low constant probability (10%) of occurrence of a deviant and a high probability (90%) of the standard tone (Javitt et al., 1996; Pincze et al., 2001; Roger et al., 2009; Ulanovsky et al., 2004, 2003), human studies often use more complex paradigms with dynamically evolving (and occasionally switching) probabilities of deviant stimuli (Baldeweg et al., 2004; Garrido et al., 2008; Haenschel et al., 2005).

Here, building upon previous studies that characterized the spatial distribution of mismatch responses to a single auditory feature (Nieto-Diego and Malmierca, 2016), we aim to broaden our understanding of predictive coding in auditory regional mapping difference across multiple acoustic features.

2. Material and methods

All experimental procedures were approved by the Committee on the Use and Care of Animals at City University of Hong Kong and under license by the Department of Health of Hong Kong [Ref. No. (17-72) in DH/SHS/8/2/5 Pt.1].

2.1 Subjects and surgical procedures

The subjects were nine female adult Wistar rats acquired from the Chinese University of Hong Kong. The rats were between 8 and 20 weeks of age (mean = 10 weeks) and weighed 200 - 310 g (mean = 238 g) at the time of the experiment. All rats were normal hearing (click ABR thresholds < 20 dB) with no prior exposure to the stimulus sequences described below. At the start of each recording experiment, we used mixture of ketamine (80 mg/kg, i.p) and xylazine (12 mg/kg, i.p) to induce anaesthesia and received an injection of the anti-inflammatory dexamethasone (0.2 mg/kg, i.p) before surgery. Body temperature was maintained with a heating pad at $36^{\circ} \pm 1$ C. This was replaced by urethane administration during subsequent recording. Ketamine + xylazine was chosen as the main surgery anaesthetic as it takes less time to induce deep anaesthesia than urethane. Urethane (0.75mg/kg, i.p) was administered about one hour after induction with the ketamine + xylazine. Therefore, ketamine + xylazine should not affect the neural activity recorded during urethane anaesthesia. This protocol is based on previous studies in rodents (Malmierca et al., 2019). The depth of anesthesia was controlled by regular testing of the toe pinch and the absence of withdrawal reflex. If required, extra doses (0.1- 0.2 ml) of urethane were administered. The anesthetized animal was placed in a stereotaxic frame in which hollow ear bars were set to deliver sound and fix head for craniotomy. The skin and muscle tissue over the right temporal side of the skull were removed. A unilateral craniotomy was performed to expose a 5 mm \times 4 mm region over the right primary auditory cortex, as shown in Figure 1 (2.5 mm posterior from the bregma, and ventral from the temporal edge of the lateral skull surface) (Doron et al., 2002; Lamas et al., 2017).

Figure 1. Experiment setup.

A) Rat brain atlas template: 8-7 mm grid projected onto a lateral view of the right hemisphere of the rat brain. Horizontal and vertical numeric values represented distance with respect to bregma (0,0) (Bakker et al., 2015). Yellow: Schematic craniotomy site including the 5 auditory cortical fields; AI(primary auditory cortex), VAF(ventral auditory field), SRAF(suprahinal auditory field), AAF(anterior auditory field), PAF(posterior auditory field) (Polley et al., 2007).

B) Photograph of a craniotomy, with superimposed drawing of the ECoG recording sites for one animal. Empty circles show the locations of the 61 ECoG electrode sites, while filled circles represent 3 reference electrodes.

2.2 Auditory paradigm

In this experiment, two consonant-vowel (CV) stimuli /da/ and /ba/ were selected from a corpus of natural speech syllables (Ives et al., 2005) and digitally edited using STRAIGHT software toolbox (Kawahara, 2006) for Matlab R2018b (Mathworks Inc., Natick, USA) to match the raw syllables for vowel duration and fundamental frequency (F0). We then used STRAIGHT to obtain stimulus tokens varying systematically in vowel duration, fundamental frequency (F0), inter-aural level differences (ILDs), and the onset consonant (/da/-/ba/, obtained by mixing the spectrograms corresponding to the two syllables at different ratios). In this study, stimulus features are largely based on previous animal studies which have investigated mismatch responses to changes in duration, pitch, ILD, or consonant (Ahmed et al., 2011; Li et al., 2019; Roger et al., 2009; Walker et al., 2009). Since the previous animal studies did not include auditory cortical mapping across different features, we selected these features for our study. There is also a precedent in the human literature (Phillips et al., 2015), which compared amplitudes and sources of mismatch responses to duration, pitch/frequency, ILD/location, as well as intensity and gap. Our initial rationale to replace e.g. intensity with another condition (consonant) was that we wanted a relatively small set of features that would have the potential to map onto distinct auditory regions; since intensity is known to modulate processing at all stages from the cochlea, we reasoned that intensity mismatch is likely to have less localised effects than other features. This set of syllables was then concatenated to generate stimulus sequences containing syllables that could vary along one of the four different features: duration, pitch, ILD, or consonant. The features were manipulated in separate blocks. In any one block, one feature could assume one of 9 different levels (durations: 55 - 95 ms in 5 ms steps; pitch mean F0: 0.7 - 1.4 kHz logarithmically spaced; ILD: -8 to +8 dB at an average binaural level of 64 dB, in 2 dB steps; consonant: /da/-/ba/, blended at ratios, from 0.1:0.9 to 0.9:0.1, in equidistant steps; see Table 1), and the remaining features fixed to an intermediate level.

Our roving oddball paradigm is adapted from Garrido et al., (2008), but differs in a few details. First, unlike the previous study, our paradigm used two speech syllables (/ba/ and /da/) instead of the pure tones. Second, we used a different number of deviant step sizes. The previous study used 7 frequency steps, from 500 to 800 Hz in 50 Hz intervals, while we used 9 different levels for each

condition. Finally, there were a few differences in stimulus parameters. Garrido et al used stimulus durations of 70 ms and inter-stimulus intervals (ISIs) of 500 ms, with around 200 trials presented for each experimental run. In our study, the stimulus duration was 55-95 ms, the ISI 300 ms, and the deviant and standard presentation yielded around 100 trials for each condition. In our roving oddball paradigm, CV stimuli were presented in continuous trains. The first CV stimulus of a train constitutes an auditory deviant, which becomes a standard after a few repetitions in a train (see Figure 2). After a number of repeat presentations drawn randomly from a uniform interval of 3 to 40 repeats, a new CV stimulus is chosen at random from the 9 possible stimulus levels shown in Table 1. The first occurrence of this new stimulus thus constitutes a “deviant” from the last stimulus of the previous train, which can be of greater or lesser magnitude depending on how much the last standard and the next deviant differ in level. This new stimulus then starts a new train of randomly chosen length, during which it becomes the new “standard”. In the analysis, neural responses were compared between the first (deviant) and last (standard) repetition of each train. This ensures that deviant and standard responses in our dataset have precisely the same stimulus parameters and number of trials. Data were acquired in 2 blocks for each condition. Each block comprised 3800 stimuli, and yielded around 50 standard and deviant presentations for each deviance magnitude. Therefore, a total of around 100 standards and deviant AEPs were averaged per condition in the analysis. Blocks for different conditions were run in a pseudo-random order, and to avoid potential deviant condition order effects, blocks were presented in a different order in each rat.

Table 1. The stimulus features and levels used in the experiment

Level	Duration (ms)	Consonant	ILD (contra- vs. ipsilateral)	Pitch (F0, kHz)
Low	55	/da/ 10% - /ba/ 90%	-8 dB	0.7071
	60	/da/ 20% - /ba/ 80%	-6 dB	0.7711
	65	/da/ 30% - /ba/ 70%	-4 dB	0.8409
	70	/da/ 40% - /ba/ 60%	-2 dB	0.9170
Intermediate	75	/da/ 50% - /ba/ 50%	0 dB	1
	80	/da/ 60% - /ba/ 40%	+2 dB	1.0905
	85	/da/ 70% - /ba/ 30%	+4 dB	1.1892
	90	/da/ 80% - /ba/ 20%	+6 dB	1.2968
High	95	/da/ 90% - /ba/ 10%	+8 dB	1.4142

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the stimulation sequences.

CV syllable sounds, represented by circles, are presented in trains of 3 to 40 repeat presentations. At the end of each train, stimulation continues with a new train starting at a different stimulus level. The first stimulus in each train (solid circles) is therefore a deviant sound, while the last (hatched circles) represents a standard sound, after the brain has adapted to the new train. In this example, the first deviant differs from the previous sequence by two levels. The second deviant differs by four levels.

2.3 ECoG data acquisition and pre-processing

ECoG recordings were performed under anaesthesia. The length of each condition was about 20 minutes. ECoG signals were recorded at a sampling rate of 24,414 Hz using a Viventri EcoG electrode array (Woods et al., 2018) connected to a Tucker Davis Technologies (TDT) PZ5 neurodigitizer and RZ2 real-time processor controlled by BrainWare. Stimuli were presented using a TDT RZ6 multiprocessor at a rate of 48,828 Hz. To extract ERPs, the recorded electrode signals were first low pass filtered at a cutoff frequency of 45 Hz using a 5th order Butterworth filter, and downsampled to 1,000 Hz. The pre-processed signals were then epoched by extracting 300 ms long voltage traces from -50 ms to +250 ms relative to the onset of each syllable in the sequence. The epoched traces were baseline corrected by subtraction of the mean voltage observed over the 50 ms before sound onset, and linearly detrended (Salisbury, 2012). To remove outliers, we calculated a standard deviation of the voltage fluctuation in each trial (SD_i) and rejected trials with SD_i beyond the median $\pm 3 SD$ of all SD_i values. This resulted in rejecting $1.08\% \pm 0.12\%$ of trials (mean $\pm SD$ across rats).

Due to individual variations in anatomy and electrode placement, we could not assume that the signals recorded from a particular electrode channel in two different animals would necessarily

reflect the activity of precisely matched, equivalent neuronal populations in each rat (see also a quantitative analysis below). We therefore calculated principal spatial and temporal components of the measured responses, and used them to reduce the dimensionality of the data. We then performed statistical analyses on these reduced data, which integrate response patterns over time or space, and are therefore less sensitive to positional mismatches than single electrode and time point data (Lan et al., 2010). Specifically, per rat and acoustic feature, we calculated single-trial difference waveforms between deviant and standard stimuli by subtracting the ECoG amplitude at each channel and time point corresponding to a standard stimulus from the amplitude corresponding to a deviant stimulus. The single-trial difference waveforms were then averaged across trials, resulting in a channel-by-time matrix of amplitude difference values. This matrix was entered into a principal component analysis, resulting in orthogonal temporal and spatial components, ordered from highest to lowest by the amount of variance they explain in the original data. The temporal and spatial components were analyzed separately. For each rat and condition, we took the first N components describing in total at least 99% variance, and calculated their weighted sum (where each component is weighted by the amount of explained variance). These weighted sums of temporal and spatial components are shown in Figure 3.

To test whether the time-series of neural responses to acoustic deviants differ from those to standards, we applied the corresponding weighted summed spatial component to the original data (channel \times time \times trial), obtaining amplitude values for each time point and trial that effectively summarized all ECoG channels according to how strongly they reflect the difference waveform. This analysis was performed separately for each rat and each condition. First, the resulting single-trial data were averaged across all trials and entered per time point into a repeated-measures ANOVA with one random factor (rat) and two fixed factors (mismatch: deviant vs. standard; condition: duration, consonant, ILD, pitch). Tests were corrected for multiple comparisons across all 300 time points (from -50 to 250 ms relative to tone onset) at a false discovery rate of 0.05 (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995). Second, having established differences between responses to standards and deviants across all conditions (see Results), we tested whether mismatch responses to different acoustic features have different latencies, by entering the rat-specific latencies (in milliseconds relative to syllable onset) of the peak mismatch responses into a repeated-measures ANOVA with one random factor (rat) and one fixed factor (condition).

Finally, we also tested whether the magnitude of mismatch responses is modulated by deviance magnitude (i.e., by how many steps each deviant differed from the preceding standard) and sign (i.e., by whether each deviant was formed by going up or down a specific acoustic feature). To this end, per time point, we averaged the single-trial difference waveforms (calculated by subtracting the amplitude of responses to standards from those to deviants) separately for each condition, for large vs. small deviance magnitudes, and for different directions of the deviance, resulting in four difference waveforms per rat and acoustic feature. These average mismatch response waveforms were entered into a repeated-measures ANOVA with one random factor (rat) and three fixed

factors (condition; step size: large vs. small; step sign: up vs. down), testing for main and interaction effects. Tests were corrected for multiple comparisons across time points as above.

Beyond comparing the time courses of responses, we also compared the spatial topographies of responses. First, we focused on the spatial principal components and tested for the relative consistency of mismatch response topographies between different acoustic features and rats. To this end, for each rat and condition, we normalized (z -scored) each spatial topography and calculated its Euclidean distance (Guggenmos et al., 2018) to either (1) the average spatial topography of the remaining conditions (acoustic features) in the same rat; or (2) the average spatial topography of the remaining rats in the same condition. Second, we tested for the relative consistency of syllable-evoked response (rather than mismatch response) topographies between different acoustic features and rats. Thus, we extracted spatial components of evoked responses (averaged per rat and condition across all trials) in an identical principal component analysis procedure as described above for the mismatch responses. Having obtained the summed weighted spatial components describing the topographies of evoked responses for each rat and condition, we calculated the same two Euclidean distance metrics as for mismatch responses above, this time quantifying the dissimilarity of evoked (rather than mismatch) responses (3) across conditions and (4) across rats. Finally, we quantified the dissimilarity between the evoked and mismatch responses by calculating, per rat and condition, (5) the Euclidean distance between the topography of an evoked response and the topography of a mismatch response. These topography distance measures were compared using paired rank-sum Wilcoxon tests in pair-wise comparisons, correcting for multiple comparisons using a Bonferroni correction.

Finally, we tested whether the topographies of mismatch responses along different acoustic features show consistent spatial distributions across channels. Per rat and condition, we extracted the 2D (dorsal-ventral and rostral-caudal) coordinates of peak electrodes showing (1) the strongest amplitude of the stimulus-evoked response and (2) the strongest amplitude of the mismatch (deviant vs. standard) waveform. To test whether mismatch responses can be mapped at a consistent angle (on the dorsal-ventral and posterior-anterior axes) relative to the spatial peak of the evoked response, we calculated the angle of the unit-normalized vector drawn between the peak of the evoked response and peak of the mismatch response, for each rat and condition. We then tested, per condition, for the clustering of rat-specific angles using the nonparametric Rayleigh z test under the null hypothesis that angles are uniformly distributed on a circle.

3. Results

3.1 Time course and topographic distribution of mismatch responses

Overall, acoustic stimuli evoked differential responses to standards vs. deviants (i.e., mismatch responses) along each of the four acoustic features (Figure 3). Given that the 61 channel ECoG

electrode array covered primary and higher-order auditory cortex regions (Doron et al., 2002; Lamas et al., 2017), we could characterize the spatial distribution of the evoked responses (averaged across standards and deviance) as well as the difference between standard and deviant responses in different conditions. The respective spatial topographies are presented in Figure 3B and C. The time courses of mismatch responses, summarizing the principal components explaining > 99% of the observed data, are presented in Figure 4A separately for each condition (acoustic feature).

Figure 3. Time courses and topographic distributions of mismatch responses to different acoustic features.

A) The time course of mismatch responses, computed as a weighted sum of principal components of difference waveforms (response to deviant minus response to standard) which explain > 99% of the original variance. The gray-shaded areas denote the SEM across rats. B) The mean topography of the evoked response, averaged across rats. C) The mean topography of the mismatch response, averaged across rats. Gray box indicated reference channel (8,57 and 64). The y-axis represented dorsal to ventral (D-V) and x-axis showed posterior to anterior (P-A).

3.2 Differences in time courses of standard and deviant responses

The spatial principal components of mismatch responses (see above) were applied to the original data (channel \times time \times trial, separately for each rat and condition) as a form of data dimensionality reduction. The resulting amplitude values, obtained for each time point and trial, effectively

summarized all ECoG channels according to how strong they reflected the difference waveform. In a repeated-measures ANOVA, we observed a significant main effect of mismatch between 17 and 193 ms (after correcting for multiple comparisons across time points at a $p < 0.05$, all $F_{1,24} > 7.256$, all uncorrected $p = 0.029$). No significant main effect of condition or interaction between mismatch and condition were observed after correcting for multiple comparisons across time points. Responses to deviants and standards for all four acoustic features are presented in Figure 4A. The latency of peak mismatch responses was not significantly different between conditions ($F_{3,24} = 0.34$, $p = 0.793$).

3.3 No effects of deviance magnitude and direction

Having established significant differences between deviants and standards across conditions, we tested whether the mismatch response depends on step size (the level of deviance: large vs. small) and sign (direction of deviance along with each stimulus feature) in another repeated-measures ANOVA. This analysis revealed no significant main or interaction effects of step size or sign, after correcting for multiple comparisons across time points ($p > 0.05$). Figure 4B shows the mismatch time courses for each condition, step size, and step sign.

Figure 4. Temporal distributions of mismatch responses through the auditory cortex in different conditions

A) The average waveform of neural responses to acoustic standards (blue) and deviants (red) in each condition (acoustic feature). The horizontal bars (gray) indicate the time points (17ms to 193ms) for which there was a statistically significant main effect of mismatch (deviant vs. standard stimuli; FDR-corrected p -value < 0.05). Since no main or interaction effects of condition were found, these time indices are the same across conditions. B) The average mismatch waveform for each deviant step size (large: thick lines; small: thin lines) and sign (up: solid lines; down: dashed

lines). No main or interaction effects were significant after correcting for multiple comparisons across time points.

3.4 Similarity between spatial topographies of mismatch and evoked responses

To compare the topographies between mismatch and evoked responses along different acoustic features, we quantified the (dis)similarity of the spatial distribution of mismatch and evoked responses between conditions (but within rats), between rats (but within conditions), and between each other (within rats and conditions). This analysis (Figure 5A, B) showed that, overall, there was more variability in response distribution between rats than between conditions (evoked responses: $Z = 4.147$, $p < 0.001$; mismatch responses: $Z = 2.938$, $p = 0.003$). Interestingly, while the variability of mismatch responses between rats was similar to the variability of evoked responses between rats ($p > 0.05$), the variability of mismatch responses between conditions was higher than the variability of evoked responses between conditions ($Z = 3.016$, $p = 0.002$). Furthermore, evoked responses were more dissimilar from mismatch responses (within rats and conditions) than from other evoked responses in different conditions (within rats; $Z = 3.927$, $p < 0.001$). Thus, the spatial distribution of mismatch responses was significantly different from the spatial distribution of the evoked responses.

To test whether the spatial distribution of mismatch responses was systematic across rats, we extracted 2D peak coordinates (dorsal-ventral and anterior-posterior) of the topographies of mismatch responses (deviant vs. standard) and evoked responses (averaged across deviants and standards) per rat and condition. Figure 5B shows the individual rats' peak coordinates of the mismatch response, relative to the peak coordinates of the evoked response, drawn as vectors with a specific length and angle. While mismatch response peaks did not overlap with the evoked response peaks (average \pm SEM vector length in mm: duration = 1.157 ± 0.257 mm; consonant = 1.389 ± 0.192 mm; ILD = 1.112 ± 0.396 mm; pitch = 1.298 ± 0.237 mm), the spatial peak of the mismatch response did not have a consistent localization (vector angle) relative to the spatial peak of the evoked response (Rayleigh z test under the null hypothesis of a uniform angle distribution: all $Z < 1.246$). In other words, for individual rats, the strongest mismatch responses for particular features appeared to occur in regions that were "off to one side" from the maximal overall evoked response, which could be interpreted to indicate particular parts of cortex being particularly involved in mismatch detection for that particular sound feature. However, such trends were not consistent across animals, and our data therefore do not support the hypothesis that particular cortical fields consistently specialize for mismatch detection in specific acoustic features such as pitch, duration or location.

Figure 5. Comparison in spatial neural response between mismatch and evoked responses in different conditions.

A) Average topography dissimilarity between conditions (left bars) and rats (right bars) for the evoked responses (light gray) and mismatch responses (dark gray). B) Average topography dissimilarity evoked responses between conditions (light gray) and evoked responses vs. mismatch responses within conditions (white) C) The difference in peak coordinates between spatial topographies of syllable-evoked responses and mismatch responses shown per condition as a vector for each rat (gray lines) along with the average vector across all rats (black line). The y-axis represented dorsal to ventral (D-V) and x-axis showed posterior to anterior (P-A).

4. Discussion

In this study, we investigated whether violations of different acoustic features (duration, consonant, ILD, and pitch) elicit mismatch responses in anesthetized rats, as well as whether these differential responses to sensory deviants vs. standards can be mapped onto different regions in the auditory cortex. To this end, we recorded neural activity using large-scale surface recordings (ECoG) over primary and higher-order auditory cortex in a roving oddball paradigm where each deviant stimulus was physically identical with a standard. This approach allowed us to find evidence for a differential time course of neural responses to sensory standards and deviants, and quantify the spatial variability of these responses between acoustic features and individual animals.

Traditionally, research on mismatch responses utilizes the classical oddball paradigm, in which a standard stimulus is assigned a high probability (e.g., 90%), and a deviant stimulus is assigned a low probability (e.g., 10%) (Garrido et al., 2009; Jaramillo et al., 2000; Naatanen, 1995). To control for physical differences between deviant and standard sounds, previous studies introduced several control conditions including a classic-reverse sequence, local-global sequence, and many standards sequences (Bekinschtein et al., 2009; El Karoui et al., 2015; Parras et al., 2017; Shiramatsu et al., 2013). However, they typically necessitate more trials, define standards and oddballs in terms of a global probability rather than local transition probability, and make the effects of stimulus repetition more challenging to study. Therefore, in this study, we used the roving paradigm which controls for physical differences between standards and deviants in an efficient way. The roving oddball paradigm has been used in several clinical studies (Boly et al., 2011; Moran et al., 2013; Rosch et al., 2019; Uhrig et al., 2014) and non-clinical human studies (Garrido et al., 2009, 2008). Only a few studies (Komatsu et al., 2015; Takaura and Fujii, 2016) used the roving oddball paradigm to investigate mismatch responses in non-human primates. Although one previous study in guinea pigs (Christianson et al., 2014) characterised mismatch responses in a roving paradigm, this study provides the first demonstration of mismatch responses in rodents in a roving oddball paradigm using multiple acoustic features. In the present study, we found mismatch responses in all acoustic features tested, with no significant latency differences between conditions. Previous studies in rodent models using simple acoustic stimuli (pure tones) observed frequency and duration deviants (Astikainen et al., 2011, 2006; Ruusuvirta et al., 1998; Tikhonravov et al., 2010, 2008). Compared to these reports, our data show earlier onset times and longer latency ranges of mismatch responses. These discrepancies may be accounted for by differences in oddball sequences and stimulus types. Our results are consistent with previous studies using syllable stimuli (Ahmed et al., 2011; Komatsu et al., 2015), which revealed earlier onset times of the mismatch response than previous studies using simple acoustic stimuli. This suggests that processing more complex sounds results influence the latency of mismatch responses in the rat model. However, previous human studies showed not only overall later-onset times and longer latency ranges of mismatch responses (Grimm et al., 2004; Jaramillo et al., 2000; Tardif et al., 2006), but also differences in latencies between stimulus features (Takegata et al., 1999). This may be explained by mismatch detection eliciting higher-order cognitive processes such as stimulus anticipation in humans (Näätänen et al., 2007), which may be more difficult to observe under anesthesia or in rodent models more generally. This suggests that the modulation of mismatch responses by stimulus features might depend on the complexity of brain networks.

While the overall differences between neural responses evoked by deviants and standards were robust for all stimulus features tested in this study, we did not observe further modulations of mismatch response amplitude by deviance magnitude or direction. The results of previous studies which tested for differences in deviance direction or magnitude (Jaramillo et al., 2000; Shelley et al., 1991; Shiramatsu et al., 2013; Takegata et al., 2008; Umbricht et al., 2005) were mutually inconsistent, which may have resulted from differences in step size between stimuli. For instance,

duration step sizes have ranged from 50 ms (Shelley et al., 1991; Umbricht et al., 2005) to 1 ms (Jaramillo et al., 2000), or from 50% (Umbricht et al., 2005) to 16% (Roger et al., 2009). Generally, rodent studies have found significant differences in mismatch response amplitude for large vs. small magnitude of deviance when step sizes were above 33% (Roger et al., 2009; Lipponen et al., 2019), while in humans these modulations can be observed even for 10% step sizes (Jaramillo et al., 2000). While our selection of step sizes was based on previous literature (Ahmed et al., 2011; Parras et al., 2017; Walker et al., 2009), taken together, the results of this and previous studies suggest that future experiments in the anesthetized rodent models should include relatively large deviance magnitudes.

On the other hand, we observed differences in spatial distribution between the mismatch responses and evoked responses, as well as between mismatch responses to different acoustic features. The variability of evoked responses between rats was similar to the variability of mismatch responses between rats, suggesting that overall the spatial distribution of mismatch responses and evoked responses could be identified with similar reliability. However, mismatch responses were more variable between conditions (acoustic features) than evoked responses. While a previous study in the ferret auditory cortex (Bizley et al., 2009) demonstrated that multiple perceptual attributes of sound, including the pitch, timbre and spatial location of the sound, can be represented by overlapping populations of neurons distributed among multiple auditory fields, our results suggest that mismatch responses to different acoustic feature are even more heterogeneous than evoked responses. This is broadly consistent with a previous microelectrode study in rat (Shiramatsu et al., 2013), reporting that the focal activation loci of evoked response were in the auditory core region, while mismatch responses had broader spatial distributions, including both core and belt regions. However, our study also shows that mismatch responses vary considerably across conditions and individual rats, consistent with a previous study in humans (Phillips et al., 2015) which found that, while multiple regions in the frontotemporal network are sensitive to auditory mismatch, the overall activity levels in single temporal and frontal regions do not differentiate between mismatch responses to different acoustic features. Taken together, these results support the notion that mismatch responses have a broad and diverse spatial distribution, similar to other higher-order functions (Herbert et al., 1991; Malmierca, 2003).

In our study, we aimed to record signals from primary and higher-order auditory regions in order to map any regional differences between mismatch responses to multiple acoustic features. However, as can be appreciated in Figure 3B and C, there was little evidence for a functional separation between regions based on the topography of the sound-evoked response, which made it difficult to delineate primary from higher-order regions based on the activity evoked by the stimuli used in this study. Even more importantly, as reported in Figure 5C, there was a large degree of heterogeneity in the relative topographies of evoked and mismatch responses across rats, again supporting the idea that the topography of observed (evoked or mismatch) responses would have been a poor ground for functional segregation of areas into primary and higher-order cortices.

Based on these results, we decided not to perform separate analyses on subgroups of channels. However, it remains a possibility that other functional mapping methods (e.g. based on tonotopic-mapping) would help in delineating the functional neuroanatomy of auditory regions in terms of primary and higher-order cortices, as indeed suggested by previous work (Higgins et al., 2010; Nieto-Diego and Malmierca, 2016; Shiramatsu et al., 2013). Therefore, it will be important to address functional separation between primary and higher-order regions in future work.

In conclusion, in the present study, we observed mismatch responses to several acoustic features, with different spatial patterns between evoked and mismatch responses, as well as between mismatch responses to different acoustic features. However, the spatial distributions of mismatch responses showed considerable differences between individual rats, suggesting that while prediction errors to different stimulus features are mediated by different neural populations (Auksztulewicz et al., 2018; Stefanics et al., 2019), these populations may not be consistently grouped into separate auditory fields at the level of primary and higher-order auditory cortices. Future work should combine neural recordings of mismatch responses in awake animals engaged in a change detection task, as well as compare the results of rodent and human studies in an identical paradigm. This would yield insights into the functional role of mismatch response variability, and shed light on the extent to which the predictive processing of different perceptual dimensions of sounds is preserved in evolution.

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